

REQUIREMENTS FOR THE REPAIR OF AUTO-MODE SUPPORT BARS IN TRUCK REPAIR SHOPS

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Annotation: Taking into account the demand for the development of the technology for repairing the auto-mode support beam of freight wagon bogies being repaired in freight wagons, applying additional technology in the bogie repair shop of the Tashkent freight wagon depo.

Key words: jackhammer, repair, cart, freight car depot, guild, puck, nut, bolt, plank, construction, category, locksmith, equipment.

Enter: After the repaired trolleys are placed under the wagon, the fastening points of the support beams are inspected.

It should be checked that the supporting beam, adjusting plate, and impact plate of the wagon are in accordance with the project documents.

Deformation and cracks in the supporting beam are not allowed.

In accordance with its construction, the support beam is fastened to the side frame using rubber-metal elements:

- M20 bolt, large-diameter washers, threaded hole, screw-on crown and simple nuts are tightened. The length of the bolt should be 90 or 100 mm according to the design of the truck, and the distance between the side frame and the bolt flange is 3 to 5 mm, and the bolt is allowed to move freely.

- or special non-standard M20 bolts (bolts with an enlarged square head), installed through a bushing path limited by a splint. The square head of the bolt is

placed perpendicularly to the diameter of the oval hole in the side frame of the wagon and is limited by the shiplint. The bolt can move freely in the direction of the oval hole. The gap between the side frame flange and the bolt should be from 1 to 3 mm.

The touching planks are fastened together with M12 bolts 60 mm long and a splint is installed. After adjusting the thickness of the plates in accordance with the state of the auto mode, the bolts are hardened to the end.

After the trolleys are inserted under the wagon and the auto mode is installed on the wagon, the distance from the center of the auto mode shaft to the edge of the supporting beam's impact plate should not be less than 50 mm on each side.

When adjusting the impact plate of the base hammer, the plates are reinforced with bolts. It is allowed to install no more than five adjustment plates with a thickness of 1.5 to 5 mm. Welding adjustment plates is prohibited [1].

Main part: It was observed that due to the presence of interruptions in the technological work process of the repair of the supporting beams, attention was not paid during the repair of trolleys in the conditions of the enterprise. Therefore, taking into account the above repair requirements, we have included an additional

technological process and a test stand offer. Accordingly, the following technical card was developed.

Technological manual on repair of defects of the main beam of freight cars by welding.

№	Execution process	Tools and equipment	Executive	Things that need to be done
1	Removing the support beam from the side frame	Wrench, hammer, baradok.	4th class plumber	Remove the support beam from the side frame, loosen the bolt shiplints attached to it, remove the bolt by unscrewing the nuts, remove the rubber-metal elements, and take it to the repair area with the help of a crane.
2	Cleaning the main beam	Wire shotka	4th class plumber	Cleaning of the support beam from rust, displaced parts, load residues up to the metal surface.
3	Inspection of welds of the support beam, welding of cracks	Welding machine VDM - 1202S Rezak R1-02 TU 304-20-14, Electrode: E42A, E46, E50A; hammer, baradok, zabula, kuvalda	5th class welder 4th class plumber	If there are cracks, the bottoms of the base hammer plate are welded, and the bends are checked for cracks. Welds are cleaned by mechanical processing.
4	The distance between the holes of the	A metal ruler, a milling machine	4th class plumber, 5th class	The distance between the holes of the support beam and the affected planks is measured

	support beam is controlled		milling machine operator.	(362±2mm). Holes are carved with the help of a milling machine.
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Due to the fact that there is no equipment in the repair shop for the repair of support beams, we have followed the process and additionally offered the following stand using scrap metal materials from the enterprise.

The law on labor protection in force in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the only procedure for organizing the development, aimed at ensuring health care and labor protection, and defines the labor protection of citizens.

During the repair and testing of the support beam, workers must observe the following safety rules.

- when removing the support hammer from the side frame, work begins with the necessary keys, hammers and bars, the keys must not be welded, the hammer handle must be made of whole wood;

- when cleaning support hammers from rust and debris, they must be cleaned with a wire brush and wear protective glasses;
- when installing the support beam on the stand, it is necessary to continue the work, making sure of the strength of the fastening screws;
- defects are visually observed, when cracks and bends are detected, they are transferred to the next repair area;
- the employee must work in special work clothes and shoes during the work process, it is not allowed to hang down the front buttons of the clothes and hang down the sleeves.

The conclusion: Today, based on our proposal, a stent has been created and put into production. Work efficiency and repair quality have been increased. A number of efficiencies have been achieved related to the workflow of the shop. Among them, changes were made to the location order, the transportation work was accelerated, and the repair time of plumber was saved.

Used literature:

1. General guide to the repair of brake equipment of wagons (Общее руководство по ремонту тормозного оборудования вагонов. Утверждено пятьдесят четвертым Советом по железнодорожному транспорту государств-участников Содружества. Протокол от 18-19 мая 2011г.)
2. Rules for labor protection during the maintenance and repair of freight cars in the wagon economy of railways «Правила по охране труда при техническом обслуживании и ремонте грузовых вагонов в вагонном хозяйстве железных дорог». Toshkent 2013-yil.
3. Google.com